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O.SH. Yormatov ., U.T. Toshtemirov

are the author of a paper titled

**METHODS FOR INCREASING HOLE DEPTH
AT A CONSTANT MINING SECTION**

Dr. Rajeev Ojha

Editor in Chief, Multidisciplinary Journal
of Science and Technology

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